

INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE CHATBOTS ON BIOLOGY TEACHERS' WORKLOAD AND JOB SATISFACTION IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of artificial intelligence chatbots on Biology teachers' workload and job satisfaction in Nigerian secondary schools, with specific focus on Akwa Ibom State. A descriptive survey research design of the correlational type was adopted. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The population comprised 1,647 Biology teachers, from which a sample of 152 teachers was selected using simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire titled AI Chatbot Influence, Workload, and Satisfaction Questionnaire (AICIWSQ). The instrument was validated by three experts in Science Education, while reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha, yielding coefficients ranging from 0.87 to 0.91 for the sections: chatbot usage, workload reduction, job satisfaction, and adoption barriers. On-the-spot retrieval method was used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that Biology teachers used AI chatbots to a high extent for instructional tasks and perceived a high extent of workload reduction. However, the influence of AI chatbot use on job satisfaction was low. The relationship between workload reduction and job satisfaction was weak and not statistically significant. Major barriers identified included poor internet connectivity, high data costs, lack of training, and absence of clear policies. It was recommended that education authorities provide training, infrastructure, clear guidelines, and improved welfare packages to support effective AI integration and enhance teachers' job satisfaction.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Chatbots, workload, job satisfaction, Biology teacher, Secondary School, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Introduction

In recent years, Nigeria's secondary school system has witnessed a steady increase in student enrolment, leading to classroom congestion, increased workload on teachers, and an overstretched instructional system (Olanrewaju & Afolabi 2022). The problem is particularly acute in the sciences, where practical-oriented subjects like Biology demand more planning time, hands-on supervision, and extensive assessment. Biology teachers are not only expected

to deliver theoretical concepts but must also organize and supervise laboratory sessions and assess practical competencies, often with limited or no laboratory support staff (Osifila & Abimbola 2020). In practice, a single Biology teacher might be assigned to handle all science classes in a school, which significantly affects the teacher's ability to prepare effectively and monitor student understanding (Osifila & Abimbola, 2020). This situation is worse in rural schools.

In addition to academic demands, Biology teachers take on numerous non-teaching responsibilities, such as compiling student results, managing attendance records, and serving as class advisers. These added duties often leave teachers exhausted, under-productive, and with little time for rest or professional development (Onaolapo et al., 2019). The consequences of these excessive demands are far-reaching, with teachers frequently reporting symptoms of burnout ranging from emotional fatigue to physical exhaustion (Osifila & Abimbola 2020). Increased death rate among teachers has also been linked to excessive workload (Onaolapo et al., 2019). This scenario is further worsened by poor infrastructure, irregular salaries, and a lack of professional recognition (Osifila & Abimbola, 2020). Without intentional reforms or the introduction of tools that support workload management, Biology teachers are at risk of long-term demotivation and professional disengagement.

At the same time, the emergence of artificial intelligence chatbots like ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and Microsoft Copilot offers teachers new ways to generate lesson content and assessments. These tools, when used effectively, have the potential to reduce repetitive tasks and free up creative energy (Chen et al., 2020; Almasri, 2024). However, the obtainable reality in Nigerian secondary schools creates a critical gap, as this adoption has not been satisfactorily linked to workload reduction (Bhojak et al., 2023). Furthermore, research is yet to sufficiently prove that AI chatbot adoption translates into a significant increase in job satisfaction (Skaalvik

& Skaalvik, 2020). Due to few research outputs and conflicting views, there was an urgent need to investigate the specific influences of AI chatbots on teacher workload and satisfaction of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to assess the influence of AI Chatbots on Biology teachers' workload and job satisfaction in Akwa Ibom State. In specific terms, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent and the specific teaching tasks for which Biology teachers use AI chatbots in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Examine the extent of workload reduction due to AI chatbots use among Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State.
3. Determine the extent of job satisfaction among Biology teachers resulting from the use of AI chatbots in Akwa Ibom State.
4. Identify the barriers that hinder AI Chatbots adoption among Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question

1. To what extent do Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State use AI chatbots for various teaching tasks?
2. To what extent does the use of AI chatbots reduce the workload of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?
3. To what extent does the use of AI-chatbots influence job satisfaction of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?
4. What are the barriers to the adoption of AI chatbots among Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the mean rating of Biology teachers on the perceived workload reduction and job satisfaction due to AI chatbots use in Akwa Ibom State.

Review of Related Literature

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as a computer's or machine's ability to complete jobs previously believed to be possible only with human intelligence (Chen et al., 2020; Coursera, 2025). It is characterized by learning, adaptability, decision-making, and problem-solving abilities (Dahiru & Zaitawa, 2025). It simulates human intelligence through machineries such as machine knowledge, neural networks, and natural language processing (Chen et al., 2020; Dahiru & Zaitawa, 2025). The speedy spread of AI across areas, including schooling, has significantly changed teaching and learning processes.

According to UNESCO, AI can address key learning challenges, modernize education and learning practices, and accelerate progress toward Sustainable Development Goal 4 - education for all (UNESCO, 2021). AI is said to enhance sustainable teaching by transforming education from a system focused on memorization to one that supports skill development through interactive learning environments (UNESCO, 2015). One major AI innovation with practical application in education is the chatbot.

AI chatbots are computer agendas that replicate human-like dialogues using text or voice interfaces (Labadze et al., 2023). They function as interactive conversational agents capable of answering questions, tutoring learners, brainstorming ideas, and engaging in natural language dialogue. In response to increasing instructional demands, AI chatbots provide support for overburdened Biology teachers by performing tasks that traditionally consume a significant

amount of teaching time (Labadze et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2021). Their use is already transforming instructional delivery, assessment, and student engagement (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Holmes et al., 2021).

In Biology education, chatbots function as virtual supporters that respond to routine student questions, deliver personalized education assistance, generate assessment rubrics, automate grading and feedback, and assist with lesson preparation. With well-crafted prompts, teachers can generate structured lesson plans aligned with curriculum objectives, which is useful when teaching multiple class streams or updating outdated materials (Mammadova et al., 2025; Zhang & Aslan, 2021). Chatbots also support differentiated instruction by generating lesson variants for different learning styles, enabling teachers to meet diverse learner needs without extensive additional planning (Smale-Jacobse et al., 2019).

Chatbots further assist with multimedia content creation by generating scripts for audio lessons, explainer videos, interactive quizzes, and presentation slides that can be saved in formats such as PowerPoint, Word, or PDF. These applications support blended and flipped classroom models, particularly in overcrowded learning environments (Feng, 2020). Additionally, chatbots serve as study companions for students, improving retention, conceptual understanding, and self-efficacy (Winkler & Söllner, 2018). They also act as instructional reviewers by evaluating lesson plans for clarity, relevance, and completeness, thereby reducing period expended on repetitive responsibilities and allowing teachers to concentrate on student interaction and instructional innovation.

Workload denotes the number and intricacy of responsibilities allotted within a specific time frame, while excessive workload occurs when job demands exceed an individual's capacity, leading to stress, burnout, and reduced well-being (Ayeni & Amanekwe, 2018). Job satisfaction means a worker's extent of cheerfulness with their work and includes attitudes toward work

roles, organizational policies, relationships, and work-life balance (Inegbedion et al., 2020). Among teachers, job satisfaction is closely linked to workload manageability, autonomy, and institutional support (Ayeni & Amanekwe, 2018).

In Nigeria, Biology teachers often face large class sizes, limited instructional time, and administrative overload, resulting in low job satisfaction and emotional exhaustion (Ayeni & Amanekwe, 2018; Onaolapo et al., 2019). When thoughtfully integrated, AI chatbots offer a pathway to improved job satisfaction by restoring teachers' control over their time. By programming monotonous duties viz: lesson design, grading, and responding to routine questions, chatbots allow teachers to focus on more fulfilling aspects of teaching, including mentoring and instructional creativity (Inegbedion et al., 2020).

Empirical studies show that teachers who use AI tools experience reduced administrative workload and increased job satisfaction, job enjoyment, and well-being (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020; Almasri, 2024). Teachers report improved morale, creativity, and professional autonomy, as well as enhanced student engagement (Bhojak et al., 2025). The reduction in workload also contributes to enriched mental health effects, including reduced anxiety and burnout (American Association of University Professors, 2022). However, AI chatbots are not substitutes for teachers; rather, they complement teaching by reducing frustration and enabling teachers to reconnect with the core purpose of education.

Despite these benefits, challenges remain. AI may increase workload through the need for supervision or correction of errors, and equity concerns arise when students lack access to digital devices (Dahiru & Zaitawa, 2025). In Nigeria, infrastructural challenges such as unstable electricity supply, poor internet connectivity, limited access to devices, and high data costs hinder adoption (Olanrewaju & Afolabi 2022). The digital divide, lack of AI training,

concerns about content accuracy, cost of premium tools, and misalignment with the Nigerian curriculum and WASSCE standards further limit effective use (Olanrewaju & Afolabi 2022).

Overall, while AI chatbots have strong potential to reduce Biology teachers' workload and enhance job satisfaction, their success depends on careful implementation, adequate infrastructure, training, and institutional support. When these conditions are met, AI chatbots can serve as valuable tools for improving teaching effectiveness and teacher well-being in Nigerian secondary schools.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design of the correlational type and was delimited to public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The target population comprised 1,647 Biology teachers employed in the 244 public secondary schools in the State, from which 152 Biology teachers (94 female and 58 male) were drawn from 5 Local Government Areas and 5 schools from each of the LGAs using a simple random sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire titled AI Chatbot Influence, Workload, and Satisfaction Questionnaire (AICIWSQ) was used for data collection after being validated by three lecturers from the Department of Science Education, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. Each section of the instrument was subjected to separate Cronbach Alpha reliability analysis, yielding indices of 0.89 for extent of chatbot use, 0.91 for workload reduction, 0.87 for job satisfaction, and 0.90 for barriers to chatbot adoption. On-the-spot retrieval method was used to administer and collect the responses by the researchers. Four research questions guided the study and were answered using mean and standard deviation, with mean scores above 2.50 indicating high extent or agreement and mean scores below 2.50 indicating low extent or disagreement. One null hypothesis was formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State use AI chatbots for various teaching tasks?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Extent of AI Chatbot Use for Teaching Tasks among Biology Teachers.

S/N	Statement (I use AI Chatbots t...)	N	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Generate initial ideas for my Biology lesson plans.	152	3.32	0.71	HE
2	Create multiple-choice or short-answer assessment questions.	152	3.41	0.68	HE
3	Produce differentiated learning materials for students with varied needs.	152	3.08	0.74	HE
4	Summarize complex research or syllabus content before teaching.	152	3.36	0.69	HE
5	Answer complex Biology questions asked by students.	152	3.15	0.77	HE
6	Draft official communications or emails to parents/administration.	152	2.21	0.83	LE
7	Develop rubrics or marking schemes for practical work.	152	2.89	0.76	HE
8	Receive suggested improvements or feedback on my lesson plans.	152	3.02	0.72	HE
9	Create engaging classroom activities or scenarios.	152	3.18	0.70	HE
10	Provide immediate, automated feedback to students on basic assignments.	152	2.32	0.79	LE
Grand Mean			3.00	0.74	HE

Results in Table 1 indicates that Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State use AI chatbots to a high extent for most instructional tasks such as lesson planning, constructing assessment, summarizing content, and creating classroom activities. However, the use of AI chatbots for drafting official communications and providing automated feedback to students was to a low extent. The grand mean score of 3.00 suggests that, overall, Biology teachers use AI chatbots to a high extent for teaching-related activities.

Research Question 2: To what extent does the use of AI chatbots reduce the workload of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Biology Teachers' Responses on the Extent to which AI Chatbots Reduce Workload.

S/N	Statement (AI Chatbots have...)	N	Mean	SD	Decision
11	Greatly reduced the time I spend on preparing lesson notes.	152	3.32	0.61	HE
12	Made it faster to generate assessment questions than doing it manually.	152	3.41	0.58	HE
13	Lowered the feeling of being overwhelmed by administrative paperwork.	152	3.18	0.66	HE
14	Allowed me to spend more time on instructional delivery rather than preparation.	152	3.36	0.60	HE
15	Reduced the need to take large volumes of school work home.	152	3.05	0.72	HE
16	Minimized the energy expended on adapting teaching materials for different classes and students with special leaning styles.	152	3.22	0.64	HE
17	Led to a decrease in time spent on routine tasks like attendance or record keeping.	152	2.05	0.88	LE
18	Provided accessible resources that quickly fill gaps in instructional materials.	152	3.38	0.59	HE
19	Made the process of marking/grading less labor-intensive.	152	3.10	0.70	HE
20	Contributed to a better overall balance between my work and personal life.	152	3.27	0.63	HE
Grand Mean			3.13	0.66	HE

The results in Table 2 indicate that Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State generally perceived the use of AI chatbots as reducing their workload to a high extent (Grand Mean = 3.13). AI chatbots were particularly effective in lesson preparation, assessment generation, and instructional support, while their influence on routine administrative tasks such as attendance and record keeping was perceived to a low extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does the use of AI-chatbots influence job satisfaction of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Biology Teachers' Job Satisfaction Due to the Use of AI Chatbots.

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	SD	Decision
21	Using AI chatbots makes my teaching tasks more enjoyable.	152	2.31	0.76	LE
22	I feel more confident and satisfied with my job when I use AI chatbots.	152	2.28	0.79	LE
23	AI chatbots help me achieve a better work–life balance, increasing my job satisfaction.	152	2.19	0.82	LE
24	I feel professionally accomplished when I successfully integrate AI chatbots into my teaching.	152	2.34	0.74	LE
25	The use of AI chatbots positively impacts my overall satisfaction as a Biology teacher.	152	2.26	0.80	LE
26	AI chatbots make it easier for me to focus on the creative and rewarding aspects of teaching.	152	2.42	0.71	LE
27	I feel more motivated in my job because I can rely on AI chatbots for routine tasks.	152	2.18	0.83	LE
28	Using AI chatbots improves my satisfaction with students' learning outcomes.	152	2.36	0.75	LE
29	I feel appreciated and recognized in my school due to my innovative use of AI chatbots.	152	1.97	0.88	LE
30	My overall job satisfaction has increased due to using AI chatbots in my teaching.	152	2.40	0.72	LE
Grand Mean			2.27	0.78	LE

Result in Table 3 indicates that the use of AI chatbots influences the job satisfaction of Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State to a low extent with a mean score of less than 2.50 for all items and a grand mean of 2.27. This suggests that while teachers may use AI chatbots for instructional support, such usage has not translated into substantial improvements in their overall job satisfaction.

Research Question 4: What are the barriers to the adoption of AI chatbots among Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Biology Teachers' Perceived Barriers to AI Chatbot Adoption.

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	SD	Decision
31	Lack of reliable internet connectivity in the school environment.	152	3.41	0.62	Agree
32	High cost of purchasing mobile data or subscribing to premium AI tools.	152	3.33	0.66	Agree
33	Lack of structured training or low digital literacy skills among teachers.	152	3.38	0.61	Agree
34	Skepticism or mistrust regarding the accuracy and reliability of AI-generated content.	152	3.25	0.69	Agree
35	Fear that the use of AI tools could be seen as academic misconduct or cheating.	152	3.18	0.72	Agree
36	Insufficient supply of necessary hardware (e.g., laptops, projectors) in the schools.	152	3.29	0.65	Agree
37	Lack of clear school policies or guidance on the ethical use of AI.	152	3.36	0.60	Agree
38	Concern that AI chatbots could eventually replace human teachers.	152	3.12	0.71	Agree
Grand Mean			3.29	0.66	Agree

Results in Table 4 indicate that Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State agree that the factors listed are barriers to adopting AI in their professional duties. The Grand mean of 3.29 shows a general agreement that internet connectivity, lack of training, mistrust of output, hardware availability, fear of adoption being considered as academic misconduct, and unclear policies among others are prominent concerns.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no significant relationship between the mean rating of Biology teachers on the perceived workload reduction and job satisfaction due to AI chatbots use in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 5: Correlation between Workload Reduction and Job Satisfaction Due to AI Chatbots Use of Biology Teachers in Akwa Ibom State.

Variable	Mean	SD	N	r	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Workload Reduction	3.13	0.66	152	0.090	150	0.272
Job Satisfaction	2.27	0.78	152			

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis shows a very weak positive relationship between perceived workload reduction and job satisfaction due to Chatbots use with $r = 0.090$. Also, with p-value of 0.272, being greater than 0.05, the results indicate that the relationship between perceived workload reduction and job satisfaction due to Chatbots use is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study provide insight into how Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State interact with AI chatbots and how these tools influence their professional lives. The discussion is organized according to the research questions and hypothesis presented in the tables.

The results in Table 1 show that Biology teachers in Akwa Ibom State use AI chatbots for instructional tasks to a high extent, with a grand mean of 3.00. Teachers frequently use chatbots to generate lesson plan ideas, create assessment questions, and summarize complex syllabus content, while use for drafting official communications and providing automated feedback was low. This high adoption is likely because Biology is a content-heavy and practical-oriented

subject that requires extensive planning, and AI allows teachers to quickly touch the multidisciplinary nature of the subject. This supports Mammadova et al. (2025) and Zhang and Aslan (2021), who noted that chatbots are highly effective for generating structured lesson plans and updating instructional materials.

As shown in Table 2, AI chatbots reduce the workload of Biology teachers to a high extent (grand mean = 3.13). Teachers reported significant time savings in lesson note preparation and assessment question generation, as chatbots automate repetitive and time-consuming tasks such as brainstorming and resource gathering. By reducing work taken home, chatbots help teachers manage overstretched instructional systems. However, their influence on attendance and record-keeping was low because these tasks remain largely manual in Nigerian public schools. This aligns with Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) and Holmes et al. (2021), who argued that AI is transforming instructional delivery and assessment by performing tasks that traditionally consume significant teaching time.

The results in Table 3 indicate that AI chatbot use influences job satisfaction of Biology teachers to a low extent (grand mean = 2.27). Teachers did not report notable increases in job enjoyment, professional accomplishment, or feeling appreciated by their schools. This may be because job satisfaction in the Nigerian context is tied to factors AI cannot fix, such as irregular salaries, poor infrastructure, delayed promotions, and lack of professional recognition. While AI chatbots reduce task-based stress, they do not address systemic environmental stressors that cause burnout. This differs from Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2020) and Almasri (2024), who suggested that AI tools generally increase job enjoyment and well-being, showing that technological efficiency alone is insufficient in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria generally.

Findings in Table 4 show strong agreement on barriers to AI adoption (grand mean = 3.29), including unreliable internet connectivity, high cost of data, lack of structured training, and

cost of premium tools, reflecting infrastructural deficits in Nigerian secondary schools. Skepticism about chatbot accuracy and fear of academic misconduct were also identified as psychological barriers, suggesting that without clear policies and digital literacy training, teachers may remain hesitant. This supports Olanrewaju and Afolabi (2022) and Dahiru and Zaitawa (2025), who emphasized that the digital divide and high costs remain major challenges to educational technology adoption in Nigeria.

Hypothesis testing in Table 5 revealed a very weak and non-significant relationship between workload reduction and job satisfaction ($r = 0.090$, $p > 0.05$), indicating that reduced workload does not necessarily translate into higher job satisfaction. This suggests that workload is only a small component of satisfaction, as financial strain and emotional toll outweigh the benefits of saved time. This aligns with Inegbedion et al. (2020), who stated that job satisfaction is a complex mix of organizational policies, work-life balance, and interpersonal relationships rather than task quantity alone.

Conclusion

This study concludes that, AI chatbots have clear potential to support Biology teachers by reducing instructional workload and enhancing teaching efficiency. However, their capacity to improve job satisfaction remains limited unless broader structural, economic, and institutional challenges within the Nigerian education system are addressed. For AI chatbots to achieve their transformative potential, their integration must be accompanied by improved infrastructure, targeted professional training, clear ethical guidelines, and reforms that enhance teachers' welfare and professional recognition.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers recommend that:

1. School administrators and education authorities should formally encourage the instructional use of AI chatbots through clear guidelines and institutional support.
2. Regular professional development programmes should be provided to train Biology teachers on effective, ethical, and curriculum-aligned use of AI chatbots.
3. Government and stakeholders should improve school internet access, subsidize data, and provide essential digital tools to support AI adoption.
4. Education authorities should establish clear policies to guide acceptable and ethical use of AI chatbots in teaching and assessment.
5. Government should set up an AI task force to monitor and address misuse of AI tools in schools.
6. Policymakers should support AI integration with broader reforms such as improved remuneration, timely promotions, and professional recognition to enhance teachers' job satisfaction.

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